

“EXPLORING THE ROLE OF POLICE IN UPHOLDING HUMAN RIGHTS AND ITS EFFECT ON THE POLICE-PUBLIC INTERFACE”

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Abstract

The paper explores the vital role of the police in upholding human rights and its impact on the police-public interface. The paper aims to explore the Role of Police concerning Human Rights and the synergy between Human Rights and Police in Law enforcement. The study adopts an explanatory research approach, utilizing secondary sources of data for comprehensive and relevant information. It delves into the origins of human rights and the significance of international treaties, highlighting the positive synergy between effective policing and human rights practices. Respecting and protecting human rights foster public trust, collaboration, and successful legal prosecutions, while violations erode trust and hinder law enforcement efforts. Community policing emerges as a solution, emphasizing community engagement, education, and proactive problem-solving. Emphasizing that police officers have human rights, adherence to these principles strengthens the police-public interface, empowering the community, and ensuring a just and secure society. By striking a balance between law enforcement and human rights, the police enhance their effectiveness and legitimacy in safeguarding justice and rights.

Keywords: Community Policing, Human Rights, Law Enforcement, Police, Police-Public Interface.

Introduction

The police, as a civic body entrusted with maintaining law and order, play a crucial role in upholding societal harmony and protecting individual rights. Without a mechanism to ensure compliance with laws and regulations, society would be plagued by constant conflict, anarchy, and confusion. In the interest of safeguarding the well-being of all citizens, laws are developed to protect individual rights, such as personal liberty, bodily integrity, freedom of expression, association, conscience, and access to justice (Mugali, 2014).

However, instances of police misconduct and human rights violations have raised concerns and sparked debates about the need for greater accountability and adherence to human rights standards. As a response to such challenges, human rights training for police officers has emerged as a widely recommended and implemented initiative aimed at enhancing police performance in this regard (Aniza, et.al., 2018).

Human rights training, often considered a stand-alone exercise, must be viewed as an essential tool within a broader strategic reform framework. It should not be perceived as an isolated goal but rather as an integral part of a comprehensive initiative to improve overall police performance and adherence to human rights principles. To achieve real impact and concrete changes in human rights performance, any training effort must be strategically designed, considering the specific skill sets of police personnel and the unique characteristics of police organizations (Kostic, et.al., 2014).

Literature Review

The literature on the theory of human rights conduct has predominantly been developed and discussed in the context of industrialized countries. However, this framework's direct applicability to developing economies, such as India, is limited due to the distinct challenges and complexities faced in these regions. The unique population pressures and the nature of economic expansion in developing nations

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hinder or even pervert the channels through which socioeconomic variables and deterrent factors work in more developed countries (Ali, 2021). As developing economies embrace economic liberalization and globalization, they create opportunities for regional economic integration and market openness. While this presents various benefits, it also opens doors for white-collar criminals to manipulate and profit from the growth of companies, particularly in the financial and capital sectors (Gehlot, 1994). The rising complexities of the business environment in these countries have raised concerns about the protection of human rights, as the impact of corporate activities on individual rights can be significant. Numerous theoretical and empirical studies have attempted to quantify the direct and indirect societal costs of crime, including its influence on economic growth. However, the research findings in this area remain inconclusive and lack a definitive consensus (Singh, 2018). The intricate relationship between crime, economic development, and human rights is subject to various contextual factors and the specific circumstances of each country, making it challenging to generalize across different regions. In the context of India and other developing economies, understanding the interplay between the protection of human rights and the role of the police becomes crucial. As the economic landscape evolves and societies navigate the complexities of globalization, it is imperative to examine how human rights training for police officers can strategically address the challenges posed by the changing patterns of crime and its impact on social and economic development (Mugali, 2014).

Objectives

1. To explore the Role of Police with regards to Human Rights.
2. To explore the synergy between Human Rights and Police with respect to Law Enforcement.

Data Source and Research Methodology

The present study adopts an explanatory research approach, seeking to investigate the role of police in relation to Human Rights and the interplay between Human Rights and law enforcement. To achieve this objective, the study primarily relies on secondary sources of data to gather comprehensive and relevant information.

The following sources are utilized for data gathering:

1. *Books*: A wide range of scholarly books, academic publications, and authoritative texts on the subject of Human Rights, law enforcement, and police conduct were accessed.
2. *Journals*: Peer-reviewed academic journals were critically analyzed to obtain up-to-date research findings, empirical studies, and expert opinions related to Human Rights issues and the role of police in various social, cultural, and political contexts.
3. *Research Articles*: Various research articles published in reputable outlets, focusing on topics related to police conduct, Human Rights violations, and strategies for enhancing police performance in respecting Human Rights, were reviewed.
4. *National Human Rights Commission*: The National Human Rights Commission is an important governmental entity responsible for promoting and defending human rights and serves as a critical primary source of information. Reports, publications, and official documents released by the commission were examined to gain a comprehensive understanding of the prevailing Human Rights challenges in the context of policing and law enforcement.

Theoretical Analysis and Implications

Origin of Human Rights

The origin of human rights can be traced to various international treaties and declarations that grant individuals their rights and liberties. Among these, the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights stands as a renowned milestone, adopted shortly after World War II. The European Convention on Human Rights also assumes significant importance which was drafted by the newly established Council of Europe after the war. The Convention aimed to implement the principles outlined in the UN declaration. It is considered a direct descendant of ancient charters, such as the Magna Carta (1215), the Bill of Rights (1689), the American Declaration of Independence (1776), and the French Declaration of the Rights of Man and the Citizen (1789), which sought to preserve and enforce rights and freedoms (*Council of Europe*, December 2013).

India has also displayed a strong commitment to the advancement and protection of human rights, exemplified by the Human Rights Commission Bill tabled in the Lok Sabha on May 14, 1992. This legislation, known as protection under the Human Rights Act, led to the establishment of the National Human Rights Commission with the primary objective of enhancing human rights protection (Singh, 2018).

Human Rights and the Police

The influence of human rights on police personnel manifests in various aspects. Police officers assist individuals whose human rights have been violated by recording their complaints and are bound by specific human rights norms while interacting with people. They hold the essential responsibility of respecting, safeguarding, and promoting the human rights of the accused in a case, ensuring that their actions do not compromise the rights of others, even if the officer is at fault. The police may, in some instances, impose restrictions on individuals' movements, but such actions must be justified and reasonable. Additionally, recognizing that police officers are human beings, their human rights must also be acknowledged and protected. Human rights play a pivotal role in shielding officers from prejudice based on caste, gender, religion, or any other discriminatory factor (Sastry, Bhujbal, 2012).

Policing and Human Rights – are not in Conflict!

Contrary to common misconceptions, the relationship between human rights and policing is not one of conflict but rather of mutual reinforcement. Human rights serve as the foundation and ultimate objective of effective policing, as they emphasize the core principles of justice, fairness, and respect for the dignity and rights of every individual. At its essence, policing is tasked with maintaining law and order, protecting citizens, and upholding the rule of law. These objectives align closely with the principles of human rights, which aim to ensure that all individuals are treated with equal rights and that their dignity is respected and protected under the law (Sharma, 2018).

Human rights-based policing operates on the premise that law enforcement actions must adhere to strict standards of legality, necessity, and proportionality. This means that police interventions must be carried out within the bounds of the law, justified by legitimate objectives, and proportionate to the situation at

hand. By adhering to these principles, the police can strike a delicate balance between enforcing the law and safeguarding individuals' rights, thereby earning public trust and support. When police actions are firmly rooted in human rights principles, it leads to a more successful administration of justice. The respect for individuals' rights ensures that evidence gathered by the police is admissible in court proceedings, strengthening the integrity of the criminal justice system. Unlawful or rights-violating actions by the police can compromise the credibility of evidence, potentially leading to the dismissal of cases or wrongful convictions (Chandrashekar, 2021).

Moreover, human rights-based policing fosters positive police-public relations. When individuals perceive that the police genuinely respect their rights and treat them with dignity, it enhances trust and cooperation with law enforcement agencies. This, in turn, encourages citizens to report crimes, assist in investigations, and actively participate in community safety initiatives. A human rights-based approach also empowers the police to address societal issues through a preventive and proactive lens. By focusing on protecting human rights, the police can identify and address root causes of crime, such as social inequality, discrimination, and lack of access to basic services. Through community engagement and collaboration, the police can work with the public to find sustainable solutions to crime and social challenges.

The Role of the Police in Human Rights

Police officers have a unique position in a democratic society since they are allowed to employ force when necessary. Human rights impose significant restrictions on police activities, involving the use of physical force, requiring them to adhere to stringent legality, the principle of proportionality and necessity standards. Such restrictions help to guarantee that when police personnel act, they carry out these operations in such a manner that upholds human rights and tries to achieve their objectives in the subtlest way possible. Police authorities have to not only uphold but actively protect human rights. Because of this police commitment to defend, human rights constitute the core of police activity.

The following are the different roles played by the police with regard to Human Rights:

Police Officers as State Officials

As state officials, police officers are obligated to safeguard human rights, which are at the heart of their work. This dedication extends to actively protecting human rights, such as arresting a suspect in order to defend the rights of others. Human rights law carries significant weight in law enforcement, guiding officers to interpret and enforce all laws in accordance with human rights norms (Marwah, 1998).

Police Officers as Law Enforcers

The ideal purpose of the police is aptly described in the international code of enforcement ethics, where their fundamental duty is to serve and protect. This entails protecting lives and property, safeguarding the innocent from deception, the weak from oppression or intimidation, and ensuring peace for all, while respecting the constitutional rights of every individual to liberty, equality, and justice (Chaudhary, 2018).

Police Officers as Protectors

As protectors, police officers hold a fundamental responsibility to ensure the safety and security of individuals within their community. This duty encompasses safeguarding the most basic and essential human rights, including the right to life, liberty, and security of the person. They intervene in violent

confrontations, provide emergency medical aid, and ensure the safety of vulnerable populations to protect the right to life. When making arrests or detaining suspects, police officers adhere to legal procedures to safeguard the right to liberty and avoid arbitrary detention (Arzt, 2016).

Police Officers as Human Rights Advocates

As human rights advocates, police officers assume a vital responsibility in their communities to promote and protect human rights for all individuals, regardless of their background or status. This role extends beyond law enforcement, encompassing community education and awareness campaigns to empower individuals with knowledge about their rights. Police officers work with marginalized and vulnerable populations, providing support, assistance, and advocacy to ensure their rights are respected. They actively combat discrimination and bias within their ranks and the community, respond to human rights violations by conducting thorough investigations and ensuring accountability, and advocate for human rights in law, policy, and professional development (*Manual on Human Rights for Police Officers*, 2011).

Reconciling Human Rights and Effective Police Work: Striking a Delicate Balance

The interplay between human rights and effective police work is a subject of debate. Some argue that human rights concerns may hinder law enforcement's efficiency, compromising their ability to combat crime effectively. However, an alternative viewpoint suggests that upholding human rights actually strengthens police work in the long run. Respecting human rights principles fosters public trust, cooperation, and legitimacy, making policing more proactive and preventive. Striking a balance between human rights and effective policing is crucial, requiring training and protocols to ensure informed decisions that uphold rights without compromising public safety.

Synergy Between Human Rights and Police with respect to Law Enforcement

The synergy between human rights and law enforcement, particularly in the context of police performance, is evident in the positive outcomes it yields. When law enforcement authorities consistently respect and protect human rights, their effectiveness in solving and preventing crimes and maintaining public order improves significantly. This respect for human rights is not only a moral and ethical obligation but also a practical necessity for law enforcement agencies.

Law enforcement's adherence to human rights principles builds public trust and encourages community collaboration. The community perceives the police as protectors of their rights, leading to successful prosecutions in court and a fair administration of justice. As a result, trust in the criminal justice system is restored, and law-abiding behavior is promoted as an example for society. Moreover, when police officers maintain a close relationship with the community, they become better equipped to prevent and solve crimes through proactive policing. This approach enhances public safety and fosters a sense of security within society. Respecting human rights also gains support from various stakeholders, including the media, the international community, and higher authorities. This support contributes to the peaceful resolution of disputes and complaints, creating an environment of cooperation and understanding (Mahendra, 2014).

Human rights standards serve as guiding principles for law enforcement agencies. The police are responsible for ensuring public safety while protecting the rights of all individuals. They should operate independently but be subject to the direction and commands of the courts. The composition of law enforcement agencies should be representative of the entire community, and officers must serve the public without bias. Law enforcement officers should not engage in political activities and must refrain from using their powers or resources to support or oppose a political organization or special interest group. They should respect and preserve the rights of all individuals and organizations without favoritism (Kolthoff, & Janssen, 2023). In exercising their rights and freedoms, individuals must be

subject only to the constraints imposed by law. Limitations on these rights should be restricted to maintain respect for others' rights and satisfy the fair necessities for law and order and general welfare in a democratic society,

Conclusion and Suggestion

The adherence to human rights principles by the police yields a multitude of positive outcomes, establishing the foundation for a just and trusted law enforcement system. When the police follow human rights standards, it fosters public trust and cooperation, encourages community collaboration, and ensures successful legal prosecutions in court. The fair administration of justice becomes a reality, setting an example for society to respect the law and its principles.

Conversely, police violations of human rights have detrimental consequences. Such actions undermine public trust in law enforcement, hinder effective prosecutions in court, and isolate the police from the community they serve. The result is the perpetuation of injustice, where guilty parties escape accountability, and victims are left without recourse. Reactive approaches to crime become the norm, as trust and collaboration with the community erode.

Recognizing the critical role of the police in promoting and preserving human rights, it becomes imperative to integrate human rights education into police training. By doing so, law enforcement agencies create the necessary foundation for a society where human rights are respected and enjoyed by all. Implementing a model that bridges theory and practice enables the realization of aspirations outlined in various human rights instruments at the international, regional, sub-regional, and national levels. Incorporating human rights into police training equips law enforcement with the tools to effectively safeguard and respect the human rights of every individual, leading to successful and trusted law enforcement outcomes.

Community Policing: Bridging the Gap between Police, Public, and Human Rights

Promoting collaboration between police and law-abiding citizens is vital for building safer and more inclusive communities. To achieve this, adopting a community relations policy and action plan becomes crucial. The plan aims to involve people from diverse backgrounds and equip officers with training to effectively handle diversity. Community outreach and public education campaigns play a significant role in fostering understanding and trust between the police and the public. Maintaining regular contact with all community groups helps bridge the gap and ensures that the police remain approachable and responsive. Creating relationships with the community through non-enforcement initiatives and assigning officers to fixed neighborhood beats strengthen police-community bonds. Increased community involvement in policing and community-based public safety programs empowers citizens to actively contribute to their own safety.

Recognizing the importance of community input, involving members in identifying issues and concerns is essential. Adopting a creative problem-solving approach enables the development of tailored solutions to specific community problems. Coordination with other government agencies and non-governmental groups ensures a comprehensive and unified effort to address community issues. The National Human Rights Commission's recommendations on police-public relations provide valuable guidance for officers, especially those stationed at police stations. These guidelines ensure that police officers carry out their duties in line with human rights standards. It is crucial to remember that police officers, like everyone else, have the same human rights. Blame should not solely fall on the police or human rights institutions; instead, both institutions must work together to uphold rights and social interests.

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